

Strategy Analysis of Sharia Network Marketing Companies (Case Study at PT HNI HPAI)

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Abstract:- This study aims to analyze the strategy used by a sharia network marketing company with a case study at PT HNI HPAI. This research was conducted with a descriptive qualitative approach where the supporting data were obtained from interviews with company leaders, market share data observations and FGD (Focus Group Discussion) together with BOD, BOC, DPS and Leaders of PT HNI HPAI. The research process in which the formulation of strategic priorities uses the input stage (IFAS, EFAS, CPM), the matching stage (IE Matrix, BCG, Grand Strategy and SWOT) and the decision stage (QSPM Matrix), resulting in the following order of strategy focus: the first, focusing on market penetration that already exists, namely by nourishing the spirit of recruitment and eliminating the obstacle, namely carrying out an operation to eradicate product dumping. Furthermore, the second priority is the market development strategy, which is targeting the millennial market and the upper middle market. Furthermore, the last or third priority is product development that will support market development, namely by developing products that are in accordance with the targeted segment. The choice of strategy must be focused and agreed to be carried out by all parties in the company, therefore by going through a systematic determination process and involving all stakeholders, will increase the involvement of all parties.

Keywords:- Strategy management, IFAS, EFAS, IE, BCG, Grand Strategy, SWOT, QSPM, Formulation Strategy.

I. INTRODUCTION

The network marketing system has become a solution for many people who do not have the capital to start a business, as well as for people who do not have special skills and also those who do not have strata of higher education. In fact, starting a business by producing something, taking care of licensing, taking care of marketing and shipping, is certainly not something easy for someone who wants to start business with a business model of producing goods / services. By running a network marketing system, someone can have a business without thinking about producing their own products, just develop and dominate the market.

Another advantage of network marketing is the human resource development side. Where network marketing teaches critical basic skills about life. Teaches humans how to stay persistent. The education is of great value. This is what I tell people "even if you don't like it, live it for 5 years, after

which you will be grateful for being ready for the real business world. But beforehand you have to get better". Their success in network marketing has a spiritual cause. They are eager to help other people's lives. If you don't have that attitude, just want income, then be an employee (Robert Kiyosaki, Rich Dad Poor Dad, 1997).

A person in the span of 3-5 years will have to work hard to build a network. The reason is that they have to nurture, provide training and motivate. Hence, dare to invest time. Instantly rich, not right in this business (Prof. Dr. Charles King, Apli Network News, vol. 5, 2017)

Meanwhile, from the company side, in addition to the product being easy to sell, the manager has insight, it must also be seen the sales history. At least, "Is the company's development fast and rewarded? Then, whether it is successful in creating and creating products and diversifying. In addition to products, from the financial side, the company must be stable, have no debts, have a good name for 3-5 years, be a member of a direct sales association, have no problems and so on. See also if the company is computerized about its distribution. Likewise, the marketing plan, which ideally allows you to recruit a lot of people (Prof. Dr. Charles King, Apli Network News, vol. 5, 2017)

PT HNI HPAI (Halal Network International – Herbal Bidder Alwahidah Indonesia) which is engaged in the field of consumer goods with a marketing model using a sharia tiered direct sales system (PLBS) is now 10 years old since its birth in of 2012. As one of the members of APLI (Indonesian Direct Sales Association) from a total of 103 other companies, PT HNI HPAI is now experiencing promising market share growth.

Fig 1. 1 Chart of the HNI market among APLI members
Source : Data from HNI Marketing Director, 2020

With an increasing market share, it shows that HNI products, which currently number around 130 products, have existed and are accepted by the people of Indonesia. By carrying out the slogan Halal is My Way, HNI targets the Muslim market segment in Indonesia in particular and in the world in general. However, even though the market share of HNI has increased among Network Marketing companies (tiered direct sales) that are members of APLI, in the last 3 years there has been a situation that must still be watched out for is a signal of a decrease in the growth rate of turnover compared to the previous year. This can be seen from the following data :

Fig 1. 2 Graph of HNI turnover growth rate compared to the previous year

Source : Data from HNI Marketing Director, 2021

PT HNI HPAI which is engaged in the field of consumer goods which is indeed a field that is experiencing growth around 2. 45% in 2021 (source: <https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/>), but what happened to HNI turnover actually decreased by 3%.

It was this situation that attracted the author to conduct research on the business growth strategy of PT HNI HPAI.

This paper is organized as follows: section 2 provides a description step of strategy formulation. Section 3 describes the data collection and provide discussion. Section 4 concludes the paper.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A company to achieve the vision and mission from the business side needs to have a strategy in facing and positioning the market segment to sell its products. Wheelen et al. (2018) submits that "business strategy focuses on improving the competitive position of the company or the products or services of a business unit in a particular industry or market segment served by the company or business unit". Business strategy is very important because research shows that the effect of business units has a doubly impact on overall company performance than the effect of a company or industry competitive business strategy (fighting against all competitors for profit) and/or cooperative (working with one or more companies for profit against other competitive actors).

Strategy as a means of a person and organization to achieve a goal, factors in success to achieve the mission and vision as the basic main factors of a business Grant and Jordan (2012) in (Herfita et al. 2017).

Strategy formulation includes developing the company's vision and mission, identifying external opportunities and threats affecting the company, determining internal strengths and weaknesses, setting long-term goals as well as generating alternative strategies and choosing strategies to be used (Fred R. David. Forest R. David 2017).

In the formulation of the strategy, there are 3 stages, namely:

A. Input Stage

At the input stage, it consists of the External Factor Evaluation (EFE) Matrix, Competitive Profile Matrix (CPM) and Internal Factor Evaluation (IFE) Matrix. This stage is a stage to summarize the information needed as the basis for formulating a strategy. The tool is used to measure subjectivity during the early stages of the strategy formulation process. Making small decisions in the input matrix regarding the relative importance of external and internal factors thus allowing strategists to generate, prioritize, evaluate, and select alternative strategies more effectively. A good intuitive assessment is always necessary in determining the right weights and ratings

B. Matching Stage

This second stage is the matching stage, where the focus is on things that are worthy of being used as a strategy and produce alternative strategies, namely by aligning external and internal factors. This stage includes swot matrix, BCG matrix, internal-external (IE) matrix and grand strategy matrix. Strategy is sometimes defined as the match made by an organization between its internal resources, capabilities, opportunities and risks created by its external factors. Tools in this stage rely on information coming from the input stage to match external opportunities and threats with internal strengths and weaknesses. Matching external and internal key factors is essential to come up with a viable alternative strategy.

C. Decision stage

It is a decision stage involving a technical single, namely the Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM). This technicality uses information from stage 1 to objectively evaluate alternative strategies identified in stage 2. QSPM is a more powerful way to determine relative attractiveness.

Fig 2. 1 Strategy Formula Analysis Framework
Source: Fred R. David. Forest R. David 2017

III. THEORITICAL FRAMEWORK

This study presents a theoretical framework as previously outlined about the strategic management flow. As the basis for the goals to be achieved, the company PT HNI HPAI has compiled its vision and mission. The **Vision** of PT HNI is to become a world-class halal industry leader (from Indonesia) while pt HNI's **Mission** is:

- Become a top network marketing company of people's pride
- To be a platform for the struggle of halal products for Muslims
- Producing entrepreneurs – Muslim entrepreneurs who can be proud of, both as marketers, network builders and producers.

To realize the vision and mission, it is necessary to establish the right strategy to realize the achievement of the company's vision and mission, preceded by an analysis step on internal conditions and external to the company at the moment. Analysis of internal conditions is very important to deal with external conditions in the form of opportunities and threats.

With the aim of facilitating the understanding of what the author will do and pour, the author uses the following framework of thinking:

Fig 3.1 Theoretical Framework
Source: Data processed 2022

IV. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

A. Input Stage

➤ *Internal Factors Analysis (IFAS)*

INTERNAL FACTORS ANALYSIS STRATEGY	Bobot	Rating	Skor
A. STRENGTHS			
1. Manajemen yang kompeten	0.18	4.0	0.72
2. Launching produk baru tiap tahun	0.16	3.5	0.57
3. Hadimya HNI Mall	0.09	1.5	0.13
4. Hadimya HNI Café	0.10	2.5	0.26
Total skor strengths (A)			1.69
B. WEAKNESSES			
1. Rekrutmen dan pembinaan menurun	0.12	1.0	0.12
2. Success Plan tidak di review	0.06	3.5	0.21
3. Kurang Training online / gagap online	0.06	3.0	0.18
4. Produk tidak cocok dengan segmen konsumen	0.10	1.0	0.10
5. Penegakan disiplin lemah, menyebabkan dumping	0.12	1.0	0.12
6. Jenuh promo	0.12	1.0	0.12
Total skor weaknesses (B)			0.85
Total Skor Faktor Internal	1.00		2.54

(A+B)

Table 4. 1 Internal Factor Analysis (IFAS)

Source: Primary Data, 2022.

Based on table 4.1 above, the total IFAS score is 2.54 out of the total score of 4.0, this shows that PT HNI HPAI still has an advantage of strength factor compared to its weaknesses. The most prominent strength of PT HNI HPAI today is the existence of competent management and the launching of new products every year. These two things are their own strengths to overcome weaknesses.

➤ *External Factors Analysis (EFAS)*

EXTERNAL FACTORS ANALYSIS STRATEGY	Bobot	Rating	Skor
OPPORTUNITIES			
1. Potensi pasar internal masih besar	0.18	3.5	0.64
2. Pasar middle-up belum tergarap	0.18	2.5	0.46
3. Pasar Milenial dan Gen Z	0.21	3.5	0.74
Total skor oportunities (A)			1.84
THREATS			
1. Produk dijual di marketplace	0.21	1.0	0.21
2. Daya beli menurun / pandemi dan harga naik	0.16	3.0	0.47
3. Pembubaran offline	0.05	4.0	0.21
Total skor threats (B)			0.89
Total Skor Faktor Eksternal	1.00		2.74

(A+B)

Table 4. 2 External Factors Analysis (EFAS)

Source: Primary Data, 2022.

Based on table 4.2 above, the total EFAS score is 2.74 out of the total score of 4.0, this shows that PT HNI HPAI still has a greater chance compared to the threats faced. The biggest opportunity is the existence of people who have been registered as members but have not or no longer use HNI products and also the market of millennial elements which is still very wide to work on .

➤ *Competitive Profile Matrix (CPM)*

As a Network Marketing company that provides consumer goods, PT HNI HPAI has a competitive profile dimension with the main indicator parameters being; Market share, Pricing, Product quality, Consumer loyalty, Distribution effectiveness, Production capacity, Experience and Technological advantages

FAKTOR STRATEGIS	BOBOT	PT HNI HPAI		N***		H*****E	
		RATING	SKOR	RATING	SKOR	RATING	SKOR
Pangsa pasar	0.09	3	0.26	2	0.17	4	0.35
Penetapan harga	0.15	4	0.61	3	0.46	2	0.30
Kualitas produk	0.17	3	0.52	2	0.35	4	0.70
Kesetiaan konsumen	0.13	3	0.39	2	0.26	2	0.26
Efektifitas distribusi	0.13	4	0.52	2	0.26	3	0.39
Kapasitas produksi	0.09	3	0.26	2	0.17	4	0.35
Pengalaman	0.11	3	0.33	2	0.22	4	0.43
Keunggulan teknologi	0.13	4	0.52	2	0.26	3	0.39
TOTAL	1.00		3.41		2.15		3.17

Table 4. 3 Competitive Profile Matrix Analysis (CPM)
Source: Primary Data, 2022.

From the CPM analysis above, it is seen that PT HNI HPAI is still ahead of existing competitors, especially from the elements: Competitive price, distribution effectiveness and technological advantages.

Meanwhile, what still needs attention to continuous improvement is on the element: product quality, which also has an impact on consumer loyalty.

B. Matching Stage

➤ *Matrik BCG*

From secondary data obtained from PT HNI HPAI, HNI's market share compared to 103 APLI members is 6.7% (in the top 10) and the direct sales market (network marketing) in Indonesia is also still growing in the range of 10%, then the conclusion that can be obtained is: the market share is high and the market growth is also high. The BCG matrix for PT HNI HPAI is in the Star/Star quadrant, as shown in the following figure 4.5:

Fig 4. 4 BCG Matrix Analysis
Source: Primary Data, 2022.

Being in the Star / Stars quadrant, PT HNI HPAI requires aggressive actions to penetrate the market and develop products, so it requires and adequate investment to do this. This is considering that the competition in this direct selling business is growing rapidly. There are many competitors who are ready to eat the market share of PT HNI HPAI, both old and new competitors.

➤ *IE Matrix*

The next stage is the matching of IE matrices used to find out the right strategic position and alternative company strategies in order to face the competition. The results of the IE matrix obtained from the IFAS and EFAS matrices are as follows:

Fig 4. 5 Results of IE Matrix Analysis
Source: Primary Data, 2022.

Based on figure 4.5 showing the results of the IE matrix analysis with an IFAS value of 2.54 and an EFAS value of 2.74, the quadrant position is quadrant V with a choice of strategies that can be taken by PT HNI HPAI is To Maintain and Hold & maintain. The various strategies that can be taken from the quadrant are Market Penetration and Product Development.

Market penetration is meant by optimizing the internal market (members) who are still not shopping for products and the internal market of Muslims who are still not members of the HNI. Market penetration must also be accompanied by product development that is in accordance with the needs of the millennial market in particular and the Muslim market in general. The action taken is to mobilize all active agents to run CAKEB (How it Works Correctly) in HNI which follows the established support system.

➤ *Matrik Grand Design*

To confirm the choice of strategy, next use a grand design analysis where the IFAS weight score is 2.54 and the EFAS weight score is 2.74. So the grand design matrix plot is in quadrant 1, namely the Aggressive strategy.

Fig 4. 6 Grand Design Matrix Analysis Results
Source: Primary Data, 2022.

Based on the Grand Design matrix analysis above, where PT HNI HPAI is included in quadrant 1, the choice of strategy that can be taken is an aggressive strategy with the following details:

1. Market development
2. Market penetration
3. Product development
4. Forward integration
5. Backward integration
6. Concentric diversification

➤ *SWOT Strategy Analysis Matrix*

The next stage of strategy matching is to conduct an FGD to discuss Strategy Analysis using the SWOT Matrix. By placing the Strengths and Weaknesses element in the top row and then placing the Opportunity and Threat element in the leftmost column, 4 quadrant boxes are created, namely SO Strategy (Strength – Opportunity), WO Strategy (Weakness and Opportunity), ST Strategy (Strength – Threat) and finally WT Strategy (Weakness – Threat).

TOWS MATRIX	STRENGTHS (S)	WEAKNESSES (W)
	<p>1. Manajemen yang kompeten</p> <p>2. Launching produk baru tiap tahun</p> <p>3. Hadirnya HNI Mall</p> <p>4. Hadirnya HNI Café</p>	<p>1. Rekrutmen dan pembinaan menurun</p> <p>2. Success Plan tidak di review</p> <p>3. Kurang Training online / gagap online</p> <p>4. Produk baru tidak cocok dengan segmen konsumen atau kualitasnya tdk terjaga</p> <p>5. Penegakan disiplin lemah, menyebabkan dumping</p> <p>6. Jenuh promo</p>
OPPORTUNITIES (O)	SO STRATEGIES	WO STRATEGIES
<p>1. Potensi pasar internal masih besar</p> <p>2. Pasar middle-up belum tergarap</p> <p>3. Pasar Milenial dan Gen Z</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Penetrasi pasar dengan pelatihan menggarap pasar middle up dan milenial (S01 – O02,03) • Memperkuat RND untuk Pengembangan produk yang sesuai segmen (S01 – O01, O02, O03) • Segera launching konsep HNI Café agar terduplikasi di setiap Halalmart (S04 – O01, O02, O03) • Iklan / endorse produk baru oleh leader2 penguasa pasar (S02 – O01) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Membuat PROMO yang memotivasi rekrut dan pembinaan (W01, W02 – O01) • Merevisi success plan baru yang lebih menyemangati (W02 – O01) • Memaksimalkan landing page HNI.id sebagai pengganti Marketplace (W03 – O01, O02, O03) • Waktu & tahapan pengembangan produk lebih seksama (W04 – O01)
THREATS (T)	ST STRATEGIES	WT STRATEGIES
<p>1. Produk dijual di marketplace</p> <p>2. Daya beli menurun / pandemi dan harga naik</p> <p>3. Pembubaran offline</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pelarangan penjualan HNI melalui marketplace (S01 – T01) • Pengembangan produk yang cost concern (S02 – T02) • Pengembangan menu2 cafe dari bahan produk2 HNI (S04 – T02) • Pengembangan produk baru HNI tetap dipertahankan uniqueness filosofi Sehat dan Halal (S02 – T01) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pelacakan melalui BP3 bukan oleh KODE dan pemberian sanksi tegas (W05 – T01)

Fig 4.7 SWOT Strategy Matrix
Source: Primary Data, 2022.

From the results of the FGD outlined in figure 4.7, then we can detail the strategy as follows:

The SO (Strength – Opportunity) strategy is as follows:

- Market penetration with training to work on the middle up and millennial markets
- Strengthening the RND for Segment-appropriate product development
- Immediately launch the HNI Café concept so that it is duplicated in every Halalmart
- Advertising / endorsement of new products by leader2 market rulers

The ST (Force – Threat) strategy is as follows:

- Prohibition of the sale of HNI through the marketplace
- Cost concern product development
- Development of menu2 café from product materials2 HNI
- The development of new HNI products is maintained by the uniqueness of the Healthy and Halal philosophy

The WO (Weakness – Opportunity) strategy is as follows:

- Create PROMO that motivates recruiting and coaching
- Revising a new, more encouraging success plan
- Maximize HNI.id landing page in place of Marketplace
- Time > stages of product development are more thorough

The WT strategy (Weakness – Threat) is as follows:

- Tracking through BP3 is not by CODE and strict sanctions are imposed

C. *Decision Stage*

➤ *QSPM Matrix Analysis*

After going through the input stage process using the IFAS, EFAS and CPM methods, then the matching stage is carried out using the IE matrix method, BCG matrix, SWOT matrix and Grand Design matrix, then finally enter the decision stage by using the QSPM matrix.

We can summarize the alternative strategy options from the matching stage as follows:

1. Market Penetration :

- Market penetration with training to work on the middle up and millennial markets
- Prohibition of the sale of HNI through the marketplace
- Revising a new, more encouraging success plan
- Tracking through BP3 is not by CODE and strict sanctions are imposed

2. Product Development :
 - Strengthening the RND for Segment-appropriate product development
 - Cost concern product development
 - The development of new HNI products is maintained by the uniqueness of the Healthy and Halal philosophy
 - Time > stages of product development are more thorough
3. Market Development
 - Immediately launch the HNI Café concept so that it is duplicated in every Halalmart
 - Advertising / endorsement of new products by leader2 market rulers
 - Development of menu2 café from product materials2 HNI
 - Create PROMO that motivates recruiting and coaching
 - Maximize HNI.id landing page in place of Marketplace

4. Future integrations
5. Integrasi kebelakang
6. Concentrated diversification (conglomeration)

Strategies number 4 to 6 are not included in the priority of discussion because they are strategies that are separate from the strategy of increasing sales turnover.

Furthermore, an interview was conducted with the Marketing Director of HNI related to the prioritization of the strategy using the QSPM matrix with the following information:

AS : Attractive Score, with the following values:

- 1 = Very disinterested
- 2 = Disinterested
- 3 = Interested
- 4 = Disinterested

TAS : Total Attractive Score

	Bobot	Strategi 1 (Market Penetration)		Strategi 2 (Product Development)		Strategi 3 (Market Development)	
		AS	TAS	AS	TAS	AS	TAS
STRENGTHS							
1. Manajemen yang kompeten	0.18	4	0.72	4	0.72	4	0.72
2. Launching produk baru tiap tahun	0.16	3	0.49	4	0.66	4	0.66
3. Hadirnya HNI Mall	0.09	2	0.18	2	0.18	2	0.18
4. Hadirnya HNI Café	0.10	3	0.31	3	0.31	3	0.31
	Bobot	Strategi 1 (Market Penetration)		Strategi 2 (Product Development)		Strategi 3 (Market Development)	
		AS	TAS	AS	TAS	AS	TAS
WEAKNESSES							
1. Rekrutmen dan pembinaan menurun	0.12	4	0.48	3	0.36	4	0.48
2. Success Plan tidak di review	0.06	2	0.12	1	0.06	2	0.12
3. Kurang Training online / gagap online	0.06	3	0.18	2	0.12	2	0.12
4. Produk tidak cocok dengan segmen konsumer	0.10	4	0.42	4	0.42	3	0.31
5. Penegakan disiplin lemah, menyebabkan c...	0.12	4	0.48	3	0.36	2	0.24
6. Jenuh promo	0.12	4	0.48	2	0.24	3	0.36
	Bobot	Strategi 1 (Market Penetration)		Strategi 2 (Product Development)		Strategi 3 (Market Development)	
		AS	TAS	AS	TAS	AS	TAS
OPPORTUNITIES							
1. Potensi pasar internal masih besar	0.18	4	0.74	3	0.55	2	0.37
2. Pasar middle-up belum tergarap	0.18	2	0.37	3	0.55	4	0.74
3. Pasar Milenial dan Gen Z	0.21	2	0.42	3	0.63	4	0.84
	Bobot	Strategi 1 (Market Penetration)		Strategi 2 (Product Development)		Strategi 3 (Market Development)	
		AS	TS	AS	TS	AS	TS
THREATS							
1. Produk dijual di marketplace	0.21	4	0.84	3	0.63	2	0.42
2. Daya beli menurun / pandemi dan harga n...	0.16	2	0.32	3	0.47	4	0.63
3. Pembubaran offline	0.05	4	0.21	2	0.11	4	0.21
TOTAL SKOR			6.75		6.37		6.70

Table 4. 4 QSPM Analysis
Source: Primary Data, 2022.

Based on the results of the QSPM Matrix Analysis in table 4.4, a sequence of strategy priorities that can be implemented according to the results of the highest to the lowest Total Attractive Score is obtained, then the order of priority is as following :

1. The first strategy is market penetration with the amount of TAS 6.75 where this strategy is carried out to optimize the internal market of Muslims who are aware of hijra, by eliminating the factor of – a factor that makes active agents weaken their recruitment power, namely the sale of HNI products in the market place, some even sell below the price. By stimulating the recruitment and coaching process, the internal market will automatically be worked on which is already in sight.
2. The 2nd strategy is market development with a total of TAS 6.70 where this strategy is carried out by opening up new markets that have not been fully worked out, namely middle-up and millennials or gen z. Strategies using influencers and strengthening landing pages are efforts to penetrate these new markets, in addition to efforts for product development that touch into segment (related to the next strategy)
3. The 3rd strategy is product development with a total of TAS 6.37 where this strategy is carried out by deepening the study before launching a new product, so that it is right on target (according to the segment) and the quality is preserved.

V. CONCLUSION

After the author completes observations, interviews, reviews of documents from various sources and analysis of data that has been received from the source, then the author can draw conclusions from the results research conducted based on research questions, including the following:

1. Identifying and analyzing the condition of internal factors (strengths and weaknesses) and external factors (opportunities and threats) of PT HNI HPAI
 - Internal Factor Analysis from PT HNI HPAI, which has a competitive advantage that is a strength in competition with other companies in terms of human resources, marketing and production that become sources of business development, namely: competence from management, consistent in launching new products every year, having the concept of HNI Mall and HNI Café. Meanwhile, weaknesses that should be watched out for are: declining levels of recruitment and coaching, saturation with existing promos and there is still an element of stuttering in the online world
 - External Factor Analysis from PT HNI HPAI is that there are still open HNI market opportunities, namely the world halal market. Internally, it is still not optimally worked on, and the middle-up segment as well as millennials and gen z. Meanwhile, the threats faced are: the rise of HNI products sold in the marketplace even at prices below agent prices, as well as the threat of decreasing people's purchasing power due to pandemic and price increases.

- Competitive Profile Matrix Analysis (CPM) provides an overview that HNI has a competitive advantage in terms of competitive prices, distribution effectiveness and technological advantages. Meanwhile, in terms of product quality, there is still room for improvement, because it can increase the value of consumer loyalty.
- 2. Analyzing and Formulating business strategy formulations to increase the turnover of PT HNI HPAI
 - From the BCG Matrix Analysis, PT HNI HPAI berada on the Star / Stars quadrant. Where PT HNI HPAI requires aggressive actions to penetrate the market and develop products, so it requires and adequate investment to do this. This is considering that the competition in this direct selling business is growing rapidly. There are many competitors who are ready to eat the market share of PT HNI HPAI, both old and new competitors.
 - From the results of the IE matrix analysis with an IFAS value of 2.54 and an EFAS value of 2.74, the quadrant position is quadrant V with a choice of strategies that can be taken by PT HNI HPAI is To Maintain and Maintain (Hold & maintain). The various strategies that can be taken from the quadrant are Market Penetration and Product Development.
 - Based on the Grand Design matrix analysis above, where PT HNI HPAI is included in quadrant 1, the choice of strategy that can be taken is an aggressive strategy with the following details:
 - Market development
 - Market penetration
 - Product development
 - Forward integration
 - Backward integration
 - Concentric diversification
 - From the results of the FGD outlined in figure 4.7, then we can detail the strategy as follows:

The SO (Strength – Opportunity) strategy is as follows:

- Market penetration with training to work on the middle up and millennial markets
- Strengthening the RND for Segment-appropriate product development
- Immediately launch the HNI Café concept so that it is duplicated in every Halalmart
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The ST (Strength – Threat) strategy is as follows:

- Prohibition of the sale of HNI through the marketplace
- Cost concern product development
- Development of menu2 café from product materials2 HNI
- The development of new HNI products is maintained by the uniqueness of the Healthy and Halal philosophy

The WO (Weakness – Opportunity) strategy is as follows:

- Create PROMO that motivates recruiting and coaching
- Revising a new, more encouraging success plan
- Maximize HNI.id landing page in place of Marketplace
- Time > stages of product development are more thorough

The WT strategy (Weakness – Threat) is as follows:

- Tracking through BP3 is not by CODE and strict sanctions are imposed
- After summarizing all strategy options into 3 groups, namely Market Penetration, Product Development and Market Development. Then the **QSPM Matrix Analysis** was carried out, then it was concluded that the priorities for implementing the strategy were:
 - The first strategy is market penetration with the amount of TAS 6.75 where this strategy is carried out to optimize the internal market of Muslims who are aware of hijra, by eliminating the factor of – a factor that makes active agents weaken their recruitment power, namely the sale of HNI products in the market place, some even sell below the price. By stimulating the recruitment and coaching process, the internal market will automatically be worked on which is already in sight.
 - The 2nd strategy is market development with a total of TAS 6.70 where this strategy is carried out by opening new markets that have not been fully worked out, namely the middle-up and generation millennials or gen z. Strategies using influencers and strengthening landing pages are efforts to penetrate these new markets, in addition to efforts for product development that touches on the segment said (related to the next strategy)
 - The 3rd strategy is product development with a total of TAS 6.37 where this strategy is carried out by deepening the study before launching a new product, so that it is right on target (according to the segment) and the quality is preserved.
- 3. Identify the right opportunities to be taken by PT HNI HPAI in order to achieve success in the process of becoming the ruler of the world halal market.

The opportunities owned by HNI, which is currently arguably one of the largest halal product providers in Indonesia, are still very large, including:

- Intergration in the future, by entering the distribution industry (expedition) to ensure that the distribution of HNI products can be more widespread.
- Carry out backward integration, by acquiring vendors and or making their own raw material needs.
- Diversifying or conglomerate, that is, entering businesses outside the main business unit, but still related to main business.

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